

D4.3 Cogwheel Workshop 1

WP4 Joint integrative projects

Responsible Partner: SVA

Contributing partners: NVI

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Starting Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Deliverable	D4.3: 1 st cogwheel workshop report with COMPARE
WP and Task	WP4; Task 4.3 – Subtask 4.3.1
Leader	Ann Lindberg (SVA)
Other contributors	Merete Hofshagen (NVI)
Due month of the deliverable	M4
Actual submission month	M5
Type <i>R: Document, report</i> <i>DEC: Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc.</i> <i>OTHER</i>	R
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public</i> <i>CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU

Report from Cogwheel Workshop 1 One Health EJP / COMPARE

Introduction

In WP4 of the One Health European Joint Programme (OHEJP), EU initiatives that require strategic interaction with OHEJP will be identified in collaboration with WP2 and WP5, to avoid redundancy and to further leverage the alignment at EU level. One of the instruments, so called cogwheel workshops (CW), are being organised by WP4 to allow key actors and relevant partners within the OHEJP, typically Project leaders or WP leaders within JRPs or JIPs, to identify synergies, joint priorities and opportunities for collaboration. It is important to identify and collect (common) JRP and JIP needs before contacting the relevant EU initiative/project and also to define if the initiative complies with these needs. Furthermore, it is important to see if the initiative can complement or assist the OHEJP, for instance with database/repositories, protocols, advice, practical collaboration (sequencing, bioinformatics, ...) and so on.

Eight CWs will be organised during the OHEJP. The reports from cogwheel workshops will be part of the input to the SRA of WP2, and the SRIA of WP7.

The target for the first CW activity was COMPARE (<http://www.compare-europe.eu>). COMPARE is a 60-month EU funded project aimed to develop an analytical framework and information sharing platform that will enable identification, containment and mitigation of emerging infectious diseases and foodborne outbreaks. The project is coordinated by DTU, an OHEJP beneficiary, and ends in 2019, by the time of the 2nd internal call of the OHEJP. The CW will ensure that OHEJP development is complementary and that potential synergies are identified at a stage when the OHEJP is starting and COMPARE is still active. Eight of COMPAREs partners are also beneficiaries in the OHEJP and will contribute to the alignment.

Practicalities

- Information about the upcoming cogwheel workshop was sent to all OHEJP Project leaders on 5 February 2018. Information about COMPARE was included.
- A total of 5 projects identified COMPARE as a relevant project to learn more about, to avoid duplication and/or to have potential for synergies with the OHEJP.
- The cogwheel workshop was held as a web meeting (Adobe Connect and Skype for business) on 12 April 2018. A physical meeting was avoided due to a potential strike in Denmark, which also served to reduce the carbon footprint. Due to the meeting format, the agenda (see annex) was not strictly followed, and the discussion took part mainly during the presentations.

Attendance list

Project	Representatives (institution)
ORION	Matthias Filter (BfR), Karin Lagesen (NVI), Fernanda Dorea (SVA)
COHESIVE	Kitty Maassen (RIVM), Charlotte Cook (APHA), Matthias Flor (BfR), Cesare Camma (IZS), Adriano di Pasquale (IZS)
IMPART	Sophie Granier (Anses)
LISTADAPT	Laurent Guillier (Anses), Karin Lagesen (NVI)
METASTAVA	Steven Van Borm (Sciensano)
WP3	Hein Imberechts (Sciensano)
WP4	Ann Lindberg (SVA), Merete Hofshagen (NVI)
COMPARE	Frank Aarestrup (DTU), Tina Hald (DTU), Håkan Vigre (DTU), Eva Møller Nielsen (SSI), Jeffrey Edward Skiby (DTU)

Output

All OHEJP projects interested in participating the cogwheel workshop had the opportunity to do so. The relevant key elements in COMPARE, as identified by each OHEJP project, are listed below. The suggested action points from each project are listed in a separate summary table below.

Meeting summary, per project

EJP Project	ORION
Relevant key elements in COMPARE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Both the data analysis pipelines developed in COMPARE, as well as new lab and bioinformatics SOPs and other infrastructural developments might be relevant. The work done along these lines in COMPARE will be taken up by the ORION project. Specifically it will be considered in ORION recommendations for working with sequencing data in conjunction with epidemiological data. The work done in COMPARE to establish harmonized data standards, e.g. to annotate samples and sampling procedures, will be of interest. The COMPARE dissemination activities might be of interest for ORION “customer” as well.
Comments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quite a few of the results from COMPARE that was of interest for ORION was still not released by the EC. Thus, we await those before further action.

EJP Project	COHESIVE
Relevant key elements in COMPARE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In COMPARE there is, reportedly, not as many real barriers to data sharing as expected (administrative, regulatory, legal). Other projects also involve data sharing (VIROGENESIS, EVAg, other projects). The report from COMPARE WP12 will be interesting. COHESIVE are not currently planning to develop any RA frameworks, but to take those that have already been developed and make sure they are being used in the right way and the results are being shared across borders. In that respect we would potentially use the RA framework developed in COMPARE as part of the ‘bag of tools’ that are on offer to risk assessors (although there will be a bias in COHESIVE to tools that are currently in active use by participants). Personnel from the same institution involved in COMPARE and COHESIVE respectively should discuss again in more detail to ensure no duplication in the two projects. Personnel from the same institutions can easily stay connected. COHESIVE has agreed to stop at the point of risk management, so there is no overlap with the risk based sampling work in COMPARE.
Comments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The online meeting platforms presented some challenges, but the Adobe connect was experienced very positively.

EJP Project	IMPART
Relevant key elements in COMPARE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IMPART-WP3 (Veterinary Pathogens MIC) and IMPART-WP4 (<i>C. difficile</i>) will generate phenotypic data. It would be of interest to complement the phenotypic data of IMPART with WGS data within COMPARE. IMPART WP5 would learn from COMPARE WP13 successful and innovative experience in providing training/webinar/e-learning materials.

EJP Project	LISTADAPT
Relevant key elements in COMPARE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP2 (WP2 Harmonised standards for sample processing and sequencing) and WP9 (COMPARE platform) were elements of interest.
Comments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> COMPARE platform may not fit to LISTADAPT need after presentation by COMPARE leaders. Alternative solutions will be envisaged (simple ENA Bioproject, JIP COHESIVE,...).

EJP Project	METASTAVA
Relevant key elements in COMPARE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Protocols for metagenomics data generation and analysis (similar models). Guidelines for workflow design. Validation data (e.g. proficiency tests, ...). Data management plan/hurdles for data sharing (e.g. legislation impact on sharing of genomic data). All of these elements are public COMPARE deliverables. Some COMPARE deliverables may not be available yet due to the project timing or delay of approval by the EC (approval seems to be linked to the end of the reporting period; 1y).

EJP Project	WP3
Relevant key elements in COMPARE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> General.

EJP Project	WP4
Relevant key elements in COMPARE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> General.
Comments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There was an interest from both sides to exchange meeting invitations, to annual meetings and other relevant meetings. There was a need expressed from COHESIVE to have a more updated project description to share with COMPARE. We have not yet defined whether JIP/JRP deliverables should be public or internal. This can be included in the OHEJP data management plan.

COMPARE	
Comments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> GENERAL: COMPARE think the OHEJP projects lacks a clearly defined plan for how to share and store especially NGS data. ORION: COMPARE think that some of the planned activities are duplication. COHESIVE: COMPARE is concerned that the institutions which can offer sharing of large data are not involved in COHESIVE. IMPART: COMPARE see potential for some fruitful collaboration, but how to share the data needs to be resolved. LISTADAPT: COMPARE think that their platform would fit LISTADAPT, since a datahub has already been created for Listeria, but COMPARE datahubs can not be offered for free. How will LISTADAPT share the expected large number of genes including phenotypic data and make it available for several partners for analyses? METASTAVA: COMPARE think there is overlap with METASTAVA.

Summary table Action points

Project	Action points	Who, when
Several	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Share information on (and attend) meetings both ways (COMPARE - EJP). Many relevant deliverables from COMPARE are not (yet) public. Check with EC (DG research/REA) what their views is on this, can they facilitate (e.g. give EJP insight in pre-validated procedures/deliverables)? Incorporate information on known data sharing hurdles (including legal issues) from COMPARE in templates/info for EJP data management plan. Discuss possibility/explore interest for setting up framework agreements with COMPARE partners regarding the utilization of certain resources/pipelines/datahubs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All, continuous OHEJP WP4 (AL), May 2018 WP4(KM/VdW/SVB), June 2018 OHEJP PMT/WP4 (AL), May 2018
ORION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explore bioinformatics pipelines, SOPs and infrastructure results from COMPARE for consideration for inclusion in the ORION project. Include COMPARE resources from Website into ORION Knowledge Hub, e.g. training courses, list of workflows, etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP2-NGS, Dec 18 WP4, continuous
COHESIVE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP1: Organize a further meeting also involving WP leaders from COMPARE to specifically discuss possible points of overlap to avoid duplication. The meeting will also clarify the choice for a new database and give detailed information about COHESIVE to COMPARE. Contact George Haringhuizen in COMPARE WP12. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> KM, CC AW, AG, asap KM, asap
IMPART	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP5 (SG) would like to explore material provided by COMPARE to get inspired and might come back to COMPARE-WP13 for advice later. WP3 and -WP4 to get in touch with COMPARE when phenotypic data are generated to explore complementarity of the 2 approaches. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SG, Summer 2018 WP3 (KV), WP4 (SM) 2nd half 2019
LISTADAPT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Formally ask WP2 leader of COMPARE for Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) for the production and analysis of WGS data produced in WP2 of COMPARE. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> LG, May 2018
METASTAVA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Action points depend on the public release date of the following COMPARE deliverables: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> SOP's for data generation and analysis. Guidelines for workflow design. Document on hurdles for data sharing. If they are soon delivered, Metastava will incorporate them in its workplan. If delivery takes too much time, Metastava will source input from its partners (who are well represented in COMPARE. E.g. FLI is COMPARE WP-leader WP2, ErasmusMC is deputy coordinator, ANSES is participant). In the latter case we will incorporate protocols etc. only from partners in our consortium. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP4
WP3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> None. 	
WP4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Investigate EFSA and ECDC's plans considering WGS and bioinformatics. Today ECDC provide WGS assistance to countries that do not have the capacity themselves. COMPARE is currently performing a pilot study in collaboration with ECDC. Duration? Continuation? Contribution to national capacity building? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> AL, May 2018

Concluding remarks

In general, the COMPARE project has activities of interest to the five OHEJP projects. The main need seems to be learning more about COMPAREs results, but concrete points for collaboration were also identified. In particular, synergies or opportunities for collaboration were seen between activities in COMPARE vs IMPART and LISTADAPT. However, a requirement is that issues regarding data sharing and infrastructure costs can be solved. From COMPAREs side, a more formal agreement would be necessary for a closer collaboration.

Furthermore, a couple of potential overlaps were identified between activities in COMPARE vs ORION and METASTAVA. Due to the fact that the workshop was held at an early stage during implementation, there is an opportunity to redirect activities where needed. This may, however, call for access to relevant COMPARE deliverables. In general, an understanding of the relatedness between the OHEJP and COMPARE could be further improved by getting access to deliverables from COMPARE, including some that are not directly publicly available. Some of the projects intend to get in contact with COMPARE for further discussions.

It was noted that although DTU is indeed an OHEJP beneficiary, there is no internal coordination between COMPARE and the OHEJP. In order to achieve better alignment, partner institutes involved in the OHEJP and other strategic initiatives should, in general, be encouraged to actively facilitate this process.

The meeting format (Adobe Connect and Skype for business) worked out quite well, although the sound was not perfect from all participants. This format could also be used for other cogwheel workshops, a bit depending on the project structure of the external project and how many EJP projects the workshop is relevant for.

The internal OHEJP meeting held after the meeting with COMPARE representatives was very constructive and allowed partners to contrast, compare and validate their impressions from the meeting with COMPARE. The meeting format also contributed positively to a sense of team building. The protocol for cogwheel workshops will be updated with these experiences.

Presentations given at the meeting

See Annex.

ANNEX

Cogwheel Workshop 1 One Health EJP / COMPARE

Item	Page
Agenda	2
Presentation COMPARE	4
Presentation ORION	35
Presentation COHESIVE	46
Presentation IMPART	56
Presentation LISTADAPT	71
Presentation METASTAVA	84

This meeting is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP.
 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

DTU Vet National Veterinary Institute <hr/>		
Grant Agreement number 773830		

Date	12 April 2018
Venue	Web meeting
Meeting	Cogwheel workshop COMPARE – One Health EJP
Room	

Meeting agenda

Objectives: To identify synergies, complementarity and potential overlaps between COMPARE activities and the work programme of funded Joint Research and Integrative Projects within the One Health EJP.

09:30-10:00	Login and preparations	All, Adobe Connect
10:00-10:05	Introduction	Ann Lindberg, SVA, WP4 leader
10:05-10:30	Presentation of COMPARE WP1 Risk assessment and risk-based strategies for sample and data collection WP2 Harmonised standards for sample processing and sequencing WP3 Sequence-based frontline clinical diagnostics WP4/7 Foodborne pathogen surveillance, outbreak detection and epidemiological analysis WP9 COMPARE platform WP12 Barriers to open data sharing WP13 Dissemination and Training	

Meeting agenda cont'd

10:30-11:20	Presentation of JRPs/JIPs:	
	10.30-10.40 ORION	
	10.40-10.50 COHESIVE	
	10.50-11.00 IMPART	
	11.00-11.10 LISTADAPT	
	11.10-11.20 METASTAVA	
11:20-11:30	Introduction to WP discussion	Merete Hofshagen, NVI
11:30-12:30	Discussion by COMPARE WP	Adobe Connect
	starting with WP2, thereafter 9, 12 (and potentially 1 and 3, depending on interest from the OHEJP).	
12:30-13:15	Lunch	
13:15-14:15	Cont'd group discussions, WP4/7.	Adobe Connect
14:15-15:00	Break	
15:00-15:45	OHEJP plenary with summary and action points, by project	Skype for business
15:45-16:00	Summary and conclusions, short evaluation	

COllaborative Management Platform for
detection and Analyses of (Re-) emerging
and foodborne outbreaks in Europe

COMPARE – Building a shared future Frank Aarestrup, Coordinator, Technical University of Denmark

This project has received funding from the *European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme* under grant agreement No 643476.

The goal

An open web-based system for improving rapid identification, containment and mitigation of emerging infectious diseases and foodborne outbreaks

- Real-time data on occurrences of all infectious agents available for all
- Tools for automatic detections of related clusters in time and space, as well as novel pathogens
- Possibilities to observe trends in clones and species as well as virulence and resistance
- Specific sequence data available to all for the development of diagnostic tests and vaccines
- There can be no real-time surveillance without real-time data-sharing

Our vision: one system serves all

System for rapid identification, containment and mitigation of emerging infectious diseases and foodborne outbreaks by generation and comparison of genomic information on samples and pathogens across sectors, time and locations, with contextual additional data.

Guiding principles:

- Cross sector
- Cross domain
- Open source
- Interaction with the rest of the World (all inclusive)
- Data for action (actionable outputs)

This project has received funding from the *European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme* under grant agreement No 643476.

Project structure

EJP – the foodborne part

Clinical:
 Diagnosis of common pathogens
 Evaluation of syndromes

Public health:
 Evaluation of syndromes
 Tracking of pathogens
 Virulence mapping

Research:
 Reservoir discovery
 Vaccine (escape)
 Resistance traits
 Transmissibility markers

1. Everyone needs to be able to sequence and get data analysed
2. Agreed mechanisms for data-sharing, give and take, some protection
3. Open source solutions

Results so far (2 years to go)

1. Uniform protocols and workflows for NGS detection of a range of viruses, bacteria and parasites in different sample types
2. Pilot studies to develop customized analytical workflows
3. First data sharing hubs for support of projects
4. Initial analysis of impact of Nagoya protocol

Relevant WPs

WP 1 Risk assessment and risk-based sampling

- Where to sample and model?
- Where might NGS be best applied in routine surveillance? How can NGS data improve our risk assessment outcomes?
- Under which scenarios should we apply NGS – which samples should we take and how many?
- Can we bring together risk specialists within public health, animals, wildlife and food?

WP1 Deliverables and milestones

Deliverables

D1.1 Automated tools for rapid assessment of key transmission parameters and rates of spread estimates. (M24 - delivered)

D1.2 Risk based surveillance plans, sampling algorithms and protocols for surveillance of emerging and foodborne diseases and pathogens not covered by existing surveillance. (M40)

D1.3 Generic risk assessment framework to target surveillance activities and outbreak investigations. (M46)

Milestones

MS6. Common protocol drafted with target pathogens and transmission modes (M12 - delivered)

MS7. Inventory of existing sampling and storage protocols completed. (M12-delivered)

WP 2 Harmonized standards for sample processing and sequencing

- To develop harmonized analytical workflows for generation of high-quality NGS data in combination with relevant metadata for pathogen detection and typing across sample types, pathogens and domains

WP 2 Deliverables and Milestones

Deliverables

- D2.1 Report on matrix-dependant sample handling protocols (M12; Nov 2015)
- D2.2 Report on standard protocol sample processing (M24; Nov 2016)
- D2.3 Report on sequencing workflow (M36; Nov. 2017)
- D2.4 Evaluated and documented data analysis pipeline (M24; Nov. 2016)
- **D2.5 Results of testing of workflow in ring trials (M36, M48, M60; Nov 2017, 2018, 2019)**

Milestones

- MS10 Performance of sequencing platforms and protocols reviewed (M18; May 2016)
- MS15 Set of core specimens prepared to be used as controls across consortium (M30; May 2017)

WP 3/6 Analytical workflows for frontline diagnostics

WP 3: To develop an analytical workflow for the use of single isolate and metagenomic NGS in human and veterinary clinical microbiology

- To develop general work-flows for integration of NGS in clinical laboratory diagnostics
- To develop a framework for prediction of phenotypic antimicrobial susceptibility based on the presence or absence of genes and mutations in sequence data
- To develop tools for identification of hospital clusters and nosocomial transmission

WP 3/6 Deliverables

Deliverables submitted:

- **D3.1** Analytical workflow for clinical diagnostic application (M18).
BacPipe Workflow
- **D3.2** Prediction algorithm for antimicrobial resistance markers in sequence data (M24).

Next deliverables (M42):

- **D3.3** Standardized protocols for detection of clusters of healthcare associated infections.
- **D6.1** Report on NGS based diagnostics in comparison to gold standard methods.

WP 4/7 Foodborne Outbreaks

- To develop a general analytical workflow for population-based disease surveillance, outbreak detection and epidemiological modelling of foodborne infections

WP 4/7 Deliverables

- already delivered

D4.1 Reference sequence database based on already available datasets

M6 (May 2015)

D7.1 Database of reference genomes of an epidemiologically relevant selection of each of the food-borne organisms in the pilot

M16 (March 2016)

D4.2. Algorithm for detection of informative (sub) types for epidemiological analysis and RA for the main food-borne pathogens.

M32 (July 2017)

D7.2 Report on NGS comparison between NGS based analysis and reference methods for cluster detection for all pilot organisms.

M36 (November 2017)

D7.3 Database of markers for host-association and ecophysiology.

M36 (November 2017)

This project has received funding from the *European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme* under grant agreement No 643476.

WP4/7 Deliverables

- Upcoming next year

D7.4 Improved guidelines for interpretation criteria for defining clusters of disease and linking of isolates from various sources and reservoirs
M48 (November 2018)

D4.3 Analytical workflow for epidemiological handling of and response to food-borne outbreaks in Europe
M48 (November 2018)

D4.4 Validated SA model for NGS data
M48 (November 2018)

D4.2. Algorithm for detection of informative (sub) types for epidemiological analysis and RA for the main food-borne pathogens

An overview of how to apply WGS data to provide meaningful data for epidemiological analysis and risk assessment

(SSI, APHA, DTU, RIVM, RKI & more)

Contents:

1. Reasons and strategies for analysis of surveillance data
2. Overview of methods to analyse sequence data
 - SNP address approach, UK
 - Elevation module, Noronet
3. Inventory of available cluster detection algorithms
4. Methods for outbreak verification and source identification
5. CASE: Use of WGS in surveillance and outbreak management of human listeriosis
6. CASE: Outbreak detection methods for Salmonella in ducks
7. Source attribution
8. Conclusion

Related Pilot

The COMPARE-ECDC pilot will assess how the data hub model of COMPARE could be used in connection to the TESSy database, in the following three-step process:

- Piloting of data sharing and storage functionalities under defined data protection agreements;
- Piloting of analytical workflows and the transfer of the derived WGS data to ECDC for joint epidemiological and genomic analysis; and
- Piloting release of defined data into a publically accessible sequence repository.

COMPARE eCDC EFSA Pilot

To determine the needs and usefulness of a platform for use by MSs to share data, compare analysis and develop intervention strategies on a national, regional level.

External

Salmonella

COMPARE has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 643476.

Global sewage metagenome project

A global snapshot of urban sewage metagenome to test for suitability for surveillance

WP 8

Contact: Rene Hendriksen (DTU)

Participants

EMC, DTU

+200 institutions

COMPARE has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 643476.

ECDC / EFSA / COMPARE pilot

WP 9 Data and Information Platform

- Multiple upload opportunities
- Web portal available
- Analysis tools available (SLIM, CGE, RIEMS, Parasite), running on data hubs automatically

Data Hubs

Data Hub	Topic	Associated Projects
dcc_sibelius	Pilot: Influenza H5N8	3
dcc_berlioz	Pilot: Ebola	1
dcc_liszt	Global Sewage	1
dcc_strauss	Kibera Sewage	1
no hub since public from onset	Copenhagen Sewage	
dcc_vivaldi	EpiData (WP4 Foodborne pathogen surveillance and epidemiological analysis)	8
dcc_schubert	AMR working group	25
dcc_beethoven	Workflow Demonstrator	3
dcc_brahms	Diagnostic metagenomics on clinical samples	1
dcc_handel	Virus metagenomics (NoV and HepA)	10
dcc_puccini	Parasites (Comparative Genomics of iNtestinal Protozoa)	1
dcc_beard	Global Sewage Virome sequencing part	1
dcc_broadbent	DTU: UNSGM proficiency test	1

This project has received funding from the *European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme* under grant agreement No 643476.

Why a central public repository?

Besides the language and altruistic issues

- The data comparison problem
- Allowing easy transfer between levels of access including public (*immediate access in war-time*)
- Allow access to bioinformatics for the frontline
 - Include the less advanced
- Allowing for constantly improving the analytic pipelines

Local server

Raw data

Epi-data

Private database

Central server

Preprocessing & Sorting (QC)

Assembly/mapping

Identification

Characterisation:
-Virulence
-Resistance
- Etc

Private Pipeline

Cluster analysis
Phlygeography

Local Programmes
(CLC, BN, etc)

Temporary private database

Shared database

ENA

- To identify, clarify and develop practical solutions for political, ethical, administrative, regulatory and legal (PEARL) barriers that hamper the timely and openly sharing of data through COMPARE

WP 12 Deliverables

- D12.1 Report on legal limitations, conditions and obligations in open data sharing. M24
- Collaborated with other EU-funded projects such as VIROGENESIS and EVAg
- Performed workshops on the activities and insights obtained in WP12 so far, and elaborated on the development of case studies.
- Delivered advice for pilot studies

WP 13 Dissemination and Training

- E-learning on www.compare-europe.eu/library/e-learning
- Workshop event for ECDC in pilot project
- Training/webinar for MSs participating in ECDC-COMPARE pilot

Future pilots beyond COMPARE partners brings opportunities for additional training/workshop events for COMPARE stakeholders

Pilot projects, running

- Antimicrobial resistance NGS workflow for diagnostic laboratories
- Diagnostic metagenomics on clinical samples
- Prediction of bacterial antimicrobial resistances from genomic data by a machine-learning approach
- NGS-based public health: foodborne pathogens (Salmonella)
- Metagenomic stool, food and environmental samples
- Avian influenza
- Geosentinel
- UNSGM
- Global sewage metagenome
 - Alternative global surveillance
 - +200 institutions, +100 countries, sampling, epidemiology, virus, bacteria, parasites
- COMPARE-ECDC-EFSA Salmonella Pilot

Publications

- More than 100 scientific articles published, acknowledging COMPARE
- Scientific articles represent all areas of COMPARE; clinical, foodborne, virus, sampling, risk assessment, barriers, cost-benefit, etc.
- See <http://www.compare-europe.eu/library/scientific-publications>

Opportunities for Collaboration

- Protocols/SOPs to be available on website soon
- Data hubs, data submission and opportunities for analysis (Code of Conduct necessary)
 - Funding?
- Pilot studies
 - Mutual relevant
- COMPARE presentations to EJP One Health

Our vision: one system serves all

Guiding principles:

- Cross sector, cross domain, open source (not commercial)
- Interaction with the rest of the world (all inclusive)
- Data for action (actionable outputs)
- Central repository (ENA, DDJ, NCBI) (bring the tools to the data)

There can be no real-time disease detection & surveillance without real-time data sharing

Cogwheel workshop

COMPARE – One Health EJP

ORION –

One health surRveillance Initiative on harmOnization of data collection and interpretation

Matthias Filter

Federal Institute for Risk Assessment, Germany

BfR, Berlin, 12th April 2018

This meeting is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

Project Partner

MS

Organisation

- BE Sciensano (formerly **CODA-CERVA** and **WIV-ISP**)
- DE German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (**BfR**)
- DE German Federal Research Institute for Animal Health (**FLI**)
- DK Technical University of Denmark Food (**DTU**)
- DK Statens Serum Institut (**SSI**)
- NL Wageningen Bioveterinary Research (**WBVR**)
- NL National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (**RIVM**)
- NO Norwegian Institute of Public Health (**NIPH**)
- NO Norwegian Veterinary Institute (**NVI**)
- SE Public Health Agency of Sweden (**FoHM**)
- SE Swedish National Veterinary Institute (**SVA**)
- UK Animal and Plant Health Agency (**APHA**)
- UK Public Health England (**PHE**)

Mission

The ORION project aims at establishing and strengthening **inter-institutional collaboration** and **transdisciplinary knowledge transfer** in the area of **surveillance data integration and interpretation**, along the One Health (OH) objective of improving health and well-being.

Objective

Prototypic implementation of an integrated **strategy for long-term consolidation and harmonization** of
One Health Surveillance (OHS)
solutions.

=> **„OHS harmonization framework“**

Work plan

Project structure

Work focus – WP1

OH Surveillance Codex –

a high level guidance for harmonised, cross-sectional description and categorisation of surveillance data covering all surveillance phases and all knowledge types.

Work focus – WP2

OHS Knowledge Hub –

a cross-domain **inventory** of **currently available data sources, methods / algorithms / tools**, that support OH surveillance data generation, data analysis, modelling and decision support

OHS Infrastructure Resources –

technical and infrastructural resources that form the basis for successful harmonization and integration of surveillance data and methods. These include harmonized data standards, software libraries, ontologies, terminology mappings, software tools supporting the adoption of the “OH Surveillance Codex”.

Acknowledgement

Thanks to the ORION coordination team:
Fernanda Dorea (SVA),
Idesbald Boone & Taras Günther (BfR)

Thanks to all ORION project partners for their support during proposal generation.

Thanks to EJP WP4, WP3, Support team

Thank you for your attention !

Email : ejp-orion@bfr.bund.de

Kick Off meeting

COHESIVE

Kitty Maassen

National Institute of Public Health and the Environment (RIVM)]

Cogwheel workshop with Compare

April 12, 2018

COHESIVE

One Health Structure in Europe

Sweden:

SVA: National Veterinary Institute Sweden

PHA: Public Health Agency

NFA: National food Agency

Italy:

IZS AM: Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale dell'Abruzzo e del Molise

IZS LER: Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale della Lombardia e dell'Emilia-Romagna

ISS: Istituto Superiore di Sanita

Germany:

Bfr: The Federal Institute for Risk Assessment

FLI: Friedrich Loeffler Institute

United Kingdom:

APHA: Animal and Plant Health Agency

PHE: Public Health England

Belgium:

CODA-CERVA: Veterinary and Agrochemical Research Centre

WIV-ISP: The Scientific Institute of Public Health

Norway:

NIPH: Norwegian Institute of Public Health

NVI: Norwegian Veterinary Institute

Austria:

AGES: The Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety

Denmark:

DTU: Technical University of Denmark

The Netherlands:

RIVM: National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (coordinator)

WBVR: Wageningen Bioveterinary Research

Background

- The emergence of zoonotic diseases
- Collaboration in signaling, response and control between the human and veterinary domain
- Systems in place in several countries
 - One Health risk-analysis structures
 - After a crisis in UK and the Netherlands
 - No blue-print
 - Involvement of government important
- Availability and accessibility of (surveillance) data
 - Sharing data cross borders
- Sharing information cross borders low profile

Objectives 1

Stimulating One Health approaches at the national level within EU countries, focusing on strengthening human-veterinary collaboration with respect to early signaling and assessing zoonotic threats.

- Best practice methods -> design common procedures and tools
- Develop systematic ways to assess zoonotic threats
- Open workshops and local short term missions

Objectives 2

*Roadmap towards an **EU zoonoses risk-assessment** or risk-analysis structure*

- Existing risk analysis and epidemiological tools, skills and facilities -> guideline, checklist
- Retrospective system analysis of detection of outbreaks
- Collaborate across country borders -> pilot between countries
- Long term risk-assessment tools (Horizon scanning)

Objectives 3

Collection and analysis of surveillance and outbreak data on (foodborne) zoonoses

- Provide IT tools and data -> outbreak situations & risk assessments
- Design, interconnect and implement databases
 - DB for WGS data
 - DB for metadata of the samples included in de WGS database
 - DB for data obtained by classical epidemiological investigations
- Development of a platform-independent tracing framework
 - Develop algorithms for tracing in outbreak situations
 - Using data from the DBs
- Development of a platform-independent risk modelling framework
- One, open source software platform
- Interoperable with the main data exchange systems

Objectives 4

Capacity building within and between EU countries

- Improved collaboration between the human and veterinary domain
- At different levels
- Within and between countries -> networks of surveillance expertise
- Several pilots /short missions

COHESIVE – One Health Structure In Europe

Collaborations

Identified collaborative partners/projects:

- ORION
- NOVA
- COMPARE
- EFSA, ECDC
- All EJP partners
- Workshops also open for non-EJP partners
-many more

Thank you for your attention !

Question?

Email : kitty.maassen@rivm.nl

IMPART

Leader : Kees Veldman
Wageningen Bioveterinary Research (WBVR)

Cogwheel EJP and COMPARE

April 2018

Represented by Sophie Granier (Anses)

IMPART

IMproving Phenotypic Antimicrobial Resistance Testing

Joint Research Project

Period: 2 years

IMPART

Thirteen partners from **nine** countries involving med, food and vet

DTU & SSI (DK), APHA & PHE (GB), ANSES (FR), PIWET (PL), SVA (SE), RIVM, WBVR & NCOH (NL), BfR (DE), NVI (NO), IZSLT (IT, external partner)

Total funding: **€1.598.116,00** (EU: €706.906,99)

IMPART, intergrative aspects

Our consortium stimulates partners from human- and animal health and food safety to join forces against AMR by sharing skills and knowledge and upgrade to a harmonized level.

IMPART

The project consists 5 work packages:

WP1: culturing of colistin resistant Enterococci

WP2: culturing of CPE

WP3: establishing new ECOFFs

WP4: disks diffusion method *C. difficile*

WP5: dissemination of knowledge

IMPART, WP1

WP leader: Sophie Granier (Anses)

Goal: harmonised method for selective isolation and detection of colistin resistant Enterobacteriaceae (*mcr*-positive isolates).

Since the first detection of mcr genes there is a growing need for a harmonised method to culture and confirm colistin resistant Enterobacteriaceae which is essential for the monitoring of the prevalence and spread of mcr in humans, animals and food.

IMPART, WP2

WP leader: Jannice Schau Slettemeås (NVI)

Goal: harmonised method for selective isolation and detection of carbapenemase resistant Enterobacteriaceae (CPE).

Numerous methods for isolation and phenotypic detection of CPE have been published, but there still is a need for a harmonized method which is essential for the monitoring of the prevalence of CPE in humans, animals and food.

IMPART, WP1/WP2

Methods for detection of colistin-resistant and carbapenem-resistant Enterobacteriaceae

IMPART, WP3

WP leader: Kees Veldman (WBVR)

Goal: setting ECOFFS for veterinary antimicrobials.

The generated data will allow the setting of ECOFFs for veterinary pathogens. Those ECOFFs will improve harmonization of monitoring of resistance in animal pathogens and support the process for defining animal specific clinical breakpoints for veterinary antimicrobials.

Establishing epidemiological cut-off values (ECOFFs)

IMPART, WP4

WP leader: Sven Maurischat (BfR)

Goal: improving susceptibility testing of *C. difficile* by optimization disk diffusion

Providing a suitable and cost-effective AST method for a broad range of antimicrobials will simplify the antimicrobial resistance surveillance for C. difficile for veterinary and human medicine.

IMPART, WP4

A collection of approximately 500 human, animal and food isolates from different European partners will be tested!

IMPART, WP5

WP leader: Kees Veldman

Goal: coordination of the four work packages and knowledge dissemination both internally within and externally beyond the IMPART consortium

IMPART, progress

Current plans:

questionnaire was send around to gather (and share) information, experiences and ideas about the different research topics (WPs).

The kick-off meeting on **20 February** at Schiphol, Amsterdam.

Question?

Email : kees.veldman@wur.nl
sophie.granier@anses.fr

Kick Off meeting

LISTADAPT: Adaptive traits of *Listeria monocytogenes* to its diverse ecological niches

Laurent GUILLIER
ANSES

Partners

P1: Anses (France)

Food safety laboratory, Salmonella Listeria Unit (L. Guillier)
Fougères laboratory, (C. Soumet, A. Bridier)
Ploufragan laboratory NGS platform (Y. Blanchard)

P2: AGES (Austria)

RL for *L. monocytogenes* (A. Pietzka)

P8: VRI (Czech republic)

NRL for *L. monocytogenes* (R. Karpiskova)

P12: DTU (Denmark)

Research Group for Genomic Epidemiology (R. Hendriksen, S. Leekitcharoen)

P18: INRA (France)

INRA Dijon UMR 1347 Agroecology (P. Piveteau)
INRA Clermont UR454 & Plate-Forme Protoemoc (M. Hébraud, M. Deveaux)

P28: IZS AM (Italy)

NRL for *L. monocytogenes* (F. Pomilio, C. Camma)

P33: NVI (Norway)

Department of Bacteriology - Food and GMO (T. Skjerdal, K. Lagesen, L. Nesse)

P36: NFA (Sweden)

NRL for *L. monocytogenes* (M. Ricão Canelhas)

Background of LISTADAPT

- *Listeria monocytogenes*:

Ubiquitous saprophyte ↔ facultative intracell. pathogen

- Still a problem for public health:

EFSA's opinion of the increase incidence of listeriosis at EU-level (EFSA 2018)

Background of LISTADAPT

- WGS

➤ Performance epidemiological investigation (Moura et al., 2016)

➤ Knowledge population structure in food (Henri et al. 2016, Maury et al., 2016), in human (Maury et al., 2016)

➤ Knowledge on virulence ... role of CC (strain-specific virulence difference) (Maury et al., 2016)

Far less is known on adaptation in environment, farm, industry (despite numerous investigation on persistence in industry)

4 objectives of LISTADAPT

1. Decipher genetic traits linked to adaptation in various ecological niches

2. Generate a database of 4000 genomes (mainly farms environment, ...)

3. Develop and implement cutting-edge methodologies (new phenotypic analysis, GWAS)

4. Make available common resources for European research

WPs of LISTADAPT

- WP1: Strain collection (existing strains + new sampling)
 - Animal
 - Country
 - Environment, farm, industry

WPs of LISTADAPT

- WP1: Strain collection (existing strains + new sampling)

One example

WPs of LISTADAPT

- WP2 : Sequencing

- Purify DNA from 2000 Lm strains including existing strain and new sampled strains
- Sequence the 2000 strains
- Assembly and annotation

De Novo assembly

WPs of LISTADAPT

- WP3: Phenotypic characterization

200 strains

- Antibiotics and biocides resistance
- Adhesion and biofilm formation
- Survival and persistence in soil microcosm
- Survival in synthetic stomach acid at 37°C
- Growth potential at cold storage temperature, low pH,...

WPs of LISTADAPT

- WP4: Identification of genetic traits in *Listeria monocytogenes* underlying adaptation to the ecological niches
 - Diversity, distribution, prevalence of clonal complexes among the reservoirs
 - Genes or genetic mechanisms responsible for adaptation, survival and virulence

WPs of LISTADAPT

- WP4: Identification of genetic traits in *Listeria monocytogenes* underlying adaptation to the ecological niches

- GWAS (snp, kmers, genes)

Niches

Phenotypes

Integrative aspects of LISTADAPT

- Environment – Animal – Food

- Reference activities – Research activities

- Phenotype – genotype

- Sharing data and methodologies

Interest for WP2 and WP9 of COMPARE

Cogwheel workshop COMPARE

METASTAVA

Standardisation and validation of metagenomic methods for the detection of foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats

Steven Van Borm

Steven.VanBorm@sciensano.be

Sciensano (formerly CODA-CERVA)

Online – hosted by DTU

12-04-2018

This meeting is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

FBZ2-METASTAVA

Project Consortium - Acknowledgements

- **Sciensano**, formerly Veterinary and Agrochemical Research Center CODA-CERVA, BE
 - Steven Van Borm^{CO, WP4, WP5}, Frank Vandebussche
 - Kris De Clercq, Andy Haegeman
- **Sciensano**, formerly Scientific Institute for Public Health WIV-ISP, BE
 - Nancy Roosens, Sigrid De Keersmaecker, Kevin Vanneste
 - Steven Van Gucht, Vanessa Suin
 - Sarah Denayer
- Friedrich Loeffler Institut **FLI**, Inst. Of Diagnostic Virology, DE
 - Martin Beer, Anne Pohlmann, Dirk Höper^{WP1}
- Swedish National Veterinary Institute **SVA**, SE
 - Lihong Liu, Mikhayil Hakhverdyan
- Netherlands Centre for One Health **NCOH**, ErasmusMC, NL
 - Marion Koopmans, Matthew Cotten, Bas Oude Munnink, Miranda de Graaf, Sander van Boheemen^{WP2}
- French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety **ANSES**, FR
 - Yannick Blanchard^{WP3}, Nicole Pavio, Sandra Martin-Latil, Isabelle Kempf

FBZ2-METASTAVA

Background & Scope

- NGS → untargeted massive parallel sequencing
 - Hypothesis free sequencing
 - Identification, characterisation
 - Multiple infection, unexpected or new species or variants
- Ongoing efforts: tool development for metagenomic data generation and analysis
 - COMPARE, EFFORT, GMI
- METASTAVA: bring metagenomics closer to diagnostic laboratories
 - Validation, quality assurance, reference data

FBZ2-METASTAVA

Principle

Sample → DNA library → NGS →

→ data QC & curation →
metagenomic analysis →
taxonomic / functional assignment
→ interpretation, follow up
research

Existing data
generation
protocols

Existing guidelines
and norms for
NGS & molecular
diagnosis

Existing data
analysis
protocols

Cross-validation
Fit-for purpose

Metrics
Internal & external
controls

Validation data
model pathogens

- Sensitivity
- Specificity
- Repeatability
- Proficiency testing

Interpretation & intercomparability
of metagenomic studies

Informed metagenomic workflow design & interpretation

FBZ2-METASTAVA

Project organisation

FBZ2-METASTAVA

Work plan

- WP1: reference data, method selection, informed metagenomic workflow design.
 - ← other projects (WP4), literature, in house and public datasets.
- WP2: Quality assurance tools for validation & interpretation
 - Quality metrics. ← norms, mining reference datasets
 - External (exogenous) control for metagenomics
 - Reproducibility & batch effects
 - Proficiency test
 - Application to parallel projects & existing datasets
- WP3: Evaluation of analytical properties (Sn, Sp) of metagenomics
 - Hepatitis E virus (pig sausage, human serum, animal fecal material)
 - Norovirus (fruit, fecal & vomit)
 - (zoonotic) DNA viruses (e.g. cowpox virus) (swabs, skin lesions)
 - Shiga toxin/verotoxin-producing Escherichia coli STEC/VTEC (food samples)
 - Detecting ABR resistance genes in diagnostic samples (pig feces)

FBZ2-METASTAVA

Links with COMPARE

- COMPARE WP2: methodology metagenomics
 - Similar model organisms
 - Protocols for data generation and analysis
- COMPARE WP12: Data protection and dissemination hurdles.
 - (Human) data/samples
 - Does COMPARE have guidelines?
- METASTAVA focus:
 - Validation of analytical properties
 - Quality metrics for informed workflow management
 - Closer to diagnostic laboratory

Thank you for your attention !

Question?

Email : Steven.VanBorm@sciensano.be

